

FOOD THE TEST IN LABORATORIES MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IMPROVEMENT

Dosmetova Gulchehra Mahkamovna

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10723499>

Abstract. This in the thesis food test in laboratories management systems in improvement current and important measures cause passed being this such as recommendations when applied give good results possible

Keywords: Food and time test laboratories, food products, quality management systems, quality assurance, audit.

Introduction: Food test in laboratories management systems important plays a role, especially considering that food products have a rapid and direct impact on human health, it is also important to check or test the quality of these types of products is considered Based on this, it is considered necessary to carry out certain works in the formation and development of the system.

Keynote: There are many ways to improve management systems in food testing laboratories.

Jesus Although 9001 does not directly address food testing, its principles Jesus Combined with 17025 compliance, it can significantly improve the management systems of such laboratories.

Fig. 1. Step-by-step improvement of the management system in food testing laboratories.

1. Planning and Awareness:

Create a cross-functional team representing different lab departments to guide implementation. All employees Jesus Organize training sessions to introduce the requirements and benefits of 9001. Quality management system clearly defining which laboratory activities and processes are covered.

2. Gap analysis:

Available to identify areas that need to be corrected quality management system Jesus Evaluation according to the requirements of 9001. Jesus According to 9001 guidelines quality management system policies, procedures and document processes. Version control and all quality management system implement a document distribution system.

3. Process improvement and implementation:

Standardized for all major laboratory activities from sampling to reporting procedures designation and collection of documents. Ensure that employees receive appropriate training to perform their duties competently in accordance with documented procedures. Establish procedures for identifying, managing, and correcting inconsistent test results or laboratory results.

4. Internal audit and management review:

Quality management system schedule periodic audits to assess performance and identify areas for improvement. To make informed decisions about improvement initiatives quality management system should regularly review its performance, including audit results and customer feedback.

5. Continuous improvement:

Identify key performance indicators that align with your lab's goals and regularly monitor progress. Implement preventive measures to eliminate identified nonconformities through corrective actions and minimize future occurrences. Creating a procedure for continuous improvement in the laboratory, encouraging innovation and employees quality management system ensuring participation in development.

By following this step-by-step plan and tailoring it to your specific lab needs, you can significantly improve your management systems, customer satisfaction, and operational excellence in your food testing lab. Jesus You can use 9001.

Continuous monitoring, evaluation, and improvement are necessary to maintain a robust and effective system that leads to long-term success.

Introduction of laboratory information management system. It is software that helps automate and simplify laboratory workflows. This can lead to improved efficiency, accuracy and outcome tracking.

Establish and follow standard operating procedures. They are written instructions that describe the steps involved in a particular laboratory procedure. By following them, laboratories can ensure that tests are performed consistently and accurately.

quality assurance audits. A quality assurance audit is a systematic review of laboratory procedures and practices. They help identify areas where improvements can be made.

Employees training on the principles of food safety and quality assurance. All personnel working in food testing laboratories must be trained in the principles of food safety and quality assurance. This helps them to understand the importance of their work and how they can contribute to food security.

By making these and other improvements, food testing laboratories help ensure the safety of the food supply and give consumers confidence in the products they buy.

Some additional tips for improving management systems in food testing laboratories:

- i.e. investing in equipment and technology. This helps improve efficiency and accuracy, and makes labs more compliant.
- creating a culture of continuous improvement. Encourage employees to identify and suggest improvements and ensure that changes are implemented in a timely manner.
- communicate effectively with stakeholders. This includes customers, regulators and the public. Trust can be built by keeping stakeholders informed about laboratory activities.

By following these tips, food testing laboratories can improve their management systems and play an important role in protecting public health. Improving management systems in food testing laboratories is critical to ensuring food safety and quality. A number of measures can be taken to improve the management system, including:

Organization of quality management system (QMS) . A QMS is a set of policies, procedures and practices designed to ensure the quality of products or services. QMS helps food testing laboratories improve their efficiency and compliance with regulatory requirements. All personnel involved in food testing must be trained in food safety and quality control procedures. This training should cover topics such as personal hygiene, sample handling and analytical techniques.

Regular audits help identify and correct any problems in the management system. The audit can be conducted by internal staff or external auditors.

A commitment to continuous improvement is essential to ensure that the management system is always up-to-date and effective. This means reviewing the system regularly and making changes as needed.

By taking these steps, food testing laboratories can improve their management systems and ensure food safety and quality.

Management system work exit or in improvement all interested parties, including employees, management, customers and regulation gives attraction to do important important have This system all interested of the parties needs satisfaction and own goals in reaching efficient to be to provide help will give.

Food tests laboratories to manage to improve help giving one series technologies there is. This technologies tasks automation, efficiency increase and errors to reduce help will give.

Management system efficiency provide for his the results determination is important. This improve need has been areas and time to determine pass with development to observe help will give.

Summary: This thesis is food test laboratories their own management systems improvements and food of products safety and quality provide great help possible.

REFERENCES

1. Ermolaeva, EO Quality management systems in the food and processing industry: monograph / EO Ermolaeva, IV Surkov. - Kemerovo: KemTIPP, 2009. - 388 p.
2. Austrian, AN Quality management in food and processing industry enterprises: textbook / AN Austrian, VM Kanter, IV Surkov, EO Ermolaeva.- 2nd edition, corrected. and extra - Novosibirsk: Sib. Univ. publishing house, 2007. - 268 p.
3. Quality management in food, processing industry, trade and catering enterprises: textbook / IV Surkov, VM Kanter, EO Ermolaeva, VM Pozniakovsky.- M.: INFRA-M, 2012.- 320 p.